

A comparative overview of generative approaches for computational form-finding of bending-active tensile structures

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Abstract

Bending-active tensile hybrid structures refer to the coupling of bending- and tension-form-active components within a unique and stiffer constructions. The variety of possible shapes applicable to the design of these structures demands new ideas around real-time physics-based simulations for the development of more flexible and interactive design spaces. This paper seeks to contribute to this research by identifying and comparing two main families of generative approaches for form-finding: geometric-driven and topology-driven. Fundamental differences of both approaches lie in the management and activation of parameters while the algorithm is running. Geometric-driven approaches are processes where form-found geometries can be variegated through dynamic alterations of metric parameters without affecting initial topological conditions. On the other hand, topology-driven approaches extend the latter by enabling differentiation through interactive adjustments of topological models. In this paper, the core ideas of geometric- and topology-driven approaches are identified and discussed. Alongside to this, the presented study serves to strategically analyse advantages and disadvantages of both approaches as well as the influence that dynamic topological models has when pursuing a solution.

Keywords: Generative design, form-finding, bending-active tensile hybrid structures, topology-driven, geometric-driven, physically-based modeling

1. Introduction

The aesthetic and material efficient qualities of bending-active tensile hybrid (BATH) structures have intrigued architects and engineers over the past decades. Considering that its geometry cannot be predicted, the task of designing such hybrid constructions is not trivial and requires a shape optimization process called form-finding. However, it may be argued that the problem scope of form-finding slightly differs between architectural and engineering disciplines in basic aspects. The engineering problem, being the most widely known, is focused on increasing the mechanical and geometrical accuracy of models. Opposite to this, the architectural problem is committed to increase design freedom by allowing to reduce accuracy in benefit of model's flexibility. As architects, the main challenge is to support the conceptual design stage through the development of highly interactive methods for addressing the exploration of structural shapes under different stresses, boundary conditions, and design constraints.

Architects generally approach the form-finding of BATH structures through analogue experimentations by adapting well-established methods originally developed by Otto's team (Gass [9]). Although analogue models permit non-comparable intuitive and interactive form-finding

processes, their limitations are evident when numerous refinements are required for satisfying design intentions and iterate over complex geometries. These conditions have constantly posed several questions about computational modeling and representational paradigms used in architectural design. The problem addresses the creation and manipulation of geometry beyond pure mathematical functions governing geometrically-constraint modeling techniques. Only recently major efforts have been devoted to the integration of particle-based methods (PBM) for the exploration of structural shapes with real-time physics.

Current efforts on integrating real-time physic-based techniques in conceptual design stages provides architects with new ways for going beyond standard shape typologies of membrane structures. In this paper two main families of generative approaches for form-finding BATH structures, categorized as geometric- and topology-driven, are identified. Generative approaches for form-finding must be perceived as computational strategies where physical accuracy may be limited in benefit of the model's flexibility for improving the design process. Therefore, the objective of this paper is to compare both families of generative approaches and analyse its advantages and disadvantages. The presented study also serves to provide a framework for the critical and practical applicability of topology-driven approaches in current design workflows.

2. Background

2.1 Bending-Active Tensile Hybrid Structures

2.1.1 Form-Finding

BATH structures refer to coupled systems of tensile form- and bending-active components in which stiffness is gained through reciprocal stress compensation and elastic deformations of parental systems (Lienhard and Knippers [17]). Such hybrid constructions include, but are not limited to, structures that integrate slender elastic beams within pre-stressed membranes. The historical review of structures using active bending presented in Gengnagel *et al.* ([16]) exposed the potential of numerical simulations for continuously creating new avenues in the exploration of BATH typologies. Lienhard and Knippers ([18]) have addressed form-finding questions by proposing three types of finite element method (FEM) strategies (Lienhard and Knippers [18]) using the contracting cable approach (Lienhard *et al.* [19]). However, FEM packages are not well suited for exploratory design purposes because input data, required during the pre-processing stage of the simulation, is typically generated through physical experimentation and/or light pre-simulations.

For these purposes, Ahlquist and Menges ([4]) developed a computational framework called springFORM that allows interactive form-finding workflows for tensile membranes structures. Simulations are then verified through close evaluations of analogue and digital models (Ahlquist and Menges [3]; Ahlquist and Fleischmann [2]) following comparable data-driven strategy used in cloth simulation (Wang *et al.* [29]). Like Kilian's CADenay software for funicular structures (Kilian and Ochsendorf [12]), springFORM implements Simon Greenwold's open source particle-spring library (Greenwold [10]). On the other hand, Van Mele *et al.* (Van Mele *et al.* [28]) have proposed a hybrid method implemented within the Rhinoceros interface that mixes dynamic relaxation (DR) and force densities for the interactive exploration of BATH structures. Other researchers have reported comparable efforts on interactive form-finding processes based on Kangaroo (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [11]; Thomsen *et al.* [23]; Schmeck and Gengnagel [25]). Among the latter, particularly interesting has been the form-conversion approach, which suggests a top-down control of form-finding since a global target geometry is predefined before starting the simulation (Schleicher and La Magna [24]). Piker ([21]) developed Kangaroo as a unified real-time physic solver for design and architecture applications. For the first release of Kangaroo (K1), a standard dynamic relaxation schema based on forces has been adopted. Here, major concepts concerning the development of the numerical solver

may be inferred from Senatore and Piker ([26]). The second release (K2), however, implements projective constraints derived from energy potentials to directly update particle's position without computing velocities' first derivatives. This approach has been proposed by Bouaziz *et al.* ([6]; [5]) by integrating rigorous continuum mechanic principles in classic position-based schemas.

2.1.2 Research Projects

In the past years, an increasing number of BATH research projects have been constructed. Taking the case of the Umbrella Marrakech (Lienhard [13]), the relative simple funnel shape of the membrane constitutes the best scenario where additional steps for shape exploration can be avoided. Because of this, the design can be solved through pure FEM routines. In fact, the designer can intuitively provide the topological data required for the pre-processing stage of the simulation. Efforts are then devoted to accurately simulate mechanical properties while conveniently restraining shape exploration.

The full potential that offer BATH structures for breaking classical formal typologies is demonstrated through projects like the Textile Hybrid M1 (Lienhard *et al.* [15]) and the Hybrid Tower (Holden Deleuran *et al.* [11]). The complex topological connectivity and geometrical shape achieved by both research projects required the development of design workflows with multiple modeling stages based on analogue, PBM and FEM models. Real-time physic-based computational models built with springFORM and K2 were respectively adopted to conduct shape exploration studies. In the case of the Textile Hybrid M1 structure which was designed with multiple scales, such computational models were used to enhance the primary structure with a secondary cell-like BATH structure to generate a double layered system (Lienhard *et al.* [14]). Yet, the computational-form-finding of the primary structure was still done with FEM by making an exhaustive use of analogues models to solve initial topological conditions. Contrary, in the case of the Hybrid Tower, PBM models were adopted for the entire form-finding of the structure. From rigorous studies on analogue models, basic system logics were derived for building a parametric model, which was then used to define initial geometrical and topological conditions. The form-finding process carried out with K2 allowed designers to finely tune metric parameters controlling dimensioning of elements and material behaviours while treating topological manipulations separately (Ramsgaard Thomsen *et al.* [23]). In other words, new topological configurations implied resetting the simulation.

Even though the Textile Hybrid M1 and the Hybrid Tower used different computational frameworks for shape exploration, minor topological changes can be addressed without an extensive use of analogue models. These research projects have demonstrated that in early design stages many design issues need to be addressed with lighter and interactive simulations. It is in this context where current efforts on PBM start to play a significant role in the development of more interactive form-finding strategies.

3. Generative Approaches for Form-Finding

It is explicitly assumed that an arbitrary geometric model is required for starting numerical form-finding. Major challenges are directly related to how well-defined those models are. Geometrical models for form-finding are described by sets of nodes/particles and ways of relating them by using metric and non-metric concepts. In this case, metric concepts are quantifiable measurements used to establish vector magnitudes for defining forces or constraints through different concepts like stiffness, angles, areas or lengths among others. On the other hand, non-metric concepts define topological relationships (Figure 1) that are used to define the type of force or constraints. Depending on the management and activation of such parameters during simulation, two main families of generative approaches for form-finding are defined.

Figure 1: Branch-node matrix storing topological relationships.

3.1 Geometric-Driven

Geometric-driven approaches are form-finding strategies where the variation of structural shapes is the result of dynamic alterations of metric properties within a persistent topological model. The form-finding problem can then be described in the context of a general static network model. Under these conditions, shape is said to be variegated since the same topology progressively derivate into a variety of different equilibrium shapes (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Shape variation within the same topological model.

Nowadays, these approaches are among the most popular strategies for form-finding mainly because numerical methods with fast convergences allow topological modification to be treated separately from the simulation. In fact, topology dynamization with active physics are error-prone operations that can easily produce numerical solutions that never converge. As a result, geometric-driven approaches may be categorized as one-directional processes (Figure 3) defined by independent modeling and simulation stages, no recursive procedures (i.e. output geometries cannot be reconverted to input models of the same numerical process) and limited capabilities for data storage modification.

Figure 3: Characteristic stages of a geometric-driven form-finding approach.

So far, most relevant examples are form-finding strategies derived from the use of Kangaroo without extended scripted functionalities. Such processes allow to conduct studies for variegating structural shapes by altering parameters controlling material and physical properties. A basic form-finding process in Kangaroo is defined by four separated stages, i.e. modeling, discretization, parameters initialization and simulation. During simulation, designers can only interfere at the third stage of the process where parameters values may be altered but not added neither deleted. The latter was analysed through custom looping scripts, which helped to determine that Kangaroo's solver sequentially stores particles and goals by index assignation within dynamic arrays. Under this structure, it is easy to add and delete items at the end of the sequence. However, it is difficult to conduct the same operations on other positions of the list without updating indexes. Altering the index sequence will inevitably require updating connectivity's data that in some circumstances make operations for adding and deleting objects complex and unsafe. Lastly, Kangaroo defines form-finding processes as data-flow diagrams with strict dependencies, and where recursive procedures have always been a challenge to implement. The latter is a well-known cost of pure data-flow models derived from visual programming languages where key routines need to be tackled through complex implementations of control-flows (Mosconi and Porta [20]).

3.2 Topology-Driven

Topology-driven approaches may be considered as extended and more generative versions of geometric-driven approaches where the form-found geometry can be differentiated through dynamic alterations of non-metric parameters. Shape differentiation refers to the dynamic process of evolving topological models during simulations (Figure 4). In this case, real-time interactions with digital models allow designers to have similar intuitive feelings as with analogue models.

Figure 4: Shape differentiation within a dynamic topological model.

Evolving network models are best suited to describe the problem of form-finding with dynamic topologies (Suzuki and Knippers [27]). These network models are used to understand and trigger changes on network's connectivities over a period of time. In doing so, detailed information regarding local and global connectivity is stored within network elements (i.e. nodes and links) and updated with each transformation. Topological dynamization implies three types of fundamental operations, i.e. addition, deletion or modification of network's connectivity. In geometric-driven approaches, these

operations are treated separately and require breaking the linear simulation process. Thus, topology-driven approaches may be categorized as circular processes (Figure 5) where problems regarding interactivity, data organization, decision-making and discretization need to be solved in parallel and recursively.

Figure 5: Design implications of a topology-driven form-finding approach.

Different researchers have recently reported the development of topology-driven approaches for form-finding. The efforts of Ahlquist *et al.* ([1]) are focused on the exploration of manual and automatic topological operations on spring-meshes for simulating complex tensile form-active systems. Here, a close analysis of the open source code of Greenwold's particle library revealed how these operations are carried at solver's level. Particle and force objects are stored through index associations within fixed sized arrays where adding and deleting elements implies sophisticated functions for updating indexes and connectivity's data. Once an array is full, the entire data structure is reconstructed for increasing its initial capacity. On the other hand, a group of researchers from CITA and KET (Quinn *et al.* [22]; Deleuran *et al.* [7]) extended K2 capabilities with custom goal scripts and proposed to use the NetworkX graph data structure for developing a computational pipeline for topology modeling of BATH structures. In both cases, physics libraries were originally designed to support static or quasi-static topological models. A different approach was presented in Suzuki and Knippers ([27]) where an entire force-based solver using a rule-based graph data structure was proposed to fully support dynamic topologic models. In this case, particle and force objects are stored through mapping associations, and not by index assignation, which drastically increase the flexibility of the schema. However, the key point is that particles are extended with additional attributes for describing its connection state within the system. From here, secure operations for topologic transformations are driven through user-defined rules formulated from the finite set of particles' states. Although these approaches are a relative a new topic in architectural design, modeling deformable objects with dynamic topological models has been already addressed for the development of surgery simulators where organs need to be cut and deformed in real-time (Delingette *et al.* [8]).

4. Examples

4.1. Example 1: Hyperbolic surface

The design of a hyper-membrane structure with a bending-active boundary is used to compare both approaches. The geometric-driven form-finding process uses K2 (Figure 6) and requires modeling an initial rectangular boundary. Since these approaches are independent of meshing algorithms, we decided to address discretization through a Catmull-Clark subdivision algorithm. Elements and parameters values for form-finding are initialized from the discretized model and the simulation is

executed. Altering parameter values immediately updates equilibrium shapes, however changing the topological model implies resetting the entire simulation.

Figure 6: Geometric-driven form-finding process using standard K2 modules.

The topology-driven form-finding process uses ElasticSpace (Figure 7), an in-house software for form-finding with dynamic topologies. Specific modeling and discretization algorithms are encapsulated in methods belonging to particles and, consequently, are hidden to users. Therefore, users directly manipulate digital objects with live physics in an equivalent way to the construction of analogue models. The process directly starts with the creation of four anchored particles which are used for the generation of a closed bending-active ring. Since the external boundary has a fixed number of particles, a paving algorithm is applied for mesh generation. The external bending-active ring and the internal tensile mesh can be easily variegated and differentiated within this schema.

Figure 7: Topology-driven form-finding process using ElasticSpace.

Although both approaches derive on the same shape, the way of addressing form-finding problems is different. In all cases where initial topological conditions can be defined or solved through designer's intuition, the geometric-driven approach is more desirable. On the other hand, the topology-driven approach fits better for exploratory modelling routines where initial topological conditions are loosely or even not defined.

4.2. Example 2: BATH_01

A self-supporting BATH structure shaped from the active combination of pre-stressed membranes within GFRP rods has been proposed. The goal of this demonstrator was to test the use topology-driven strategies for form-finding and exploring new material articulations within the existing world of BATH structures (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Form-finding sequence based on a dynamic topological model.

The final geometric configuration of the structure was carried in ElasticSpace using force-based dynamics (Figure 9) where studies for differentiation are mainly driven by dynamic alterations of topological data during algorithm's runtime. The structure exists out of three structural parts: the column/mast that is constructed by 4 drop-shaped splines and form a steady base, the membrane that is partially connect to the base structure, and the boundary edge spline that tensions the membrane is kept in mid-air by the pre-stress of the membrane. All forces acting on the structure are solved internally so that there are no reaction forces towards the ground or surroundings. The geometry of all components is varied and optimized to its specific structural behaviour.

Figure 9: BATH structure form-found through ElasticSpace.

5. Conclusions

The exploration of design spaces in numerical form-finding is only limited by designer's intuition and creativity. The research presented in this paper identified and compared the two main families of generative approaches for form-finding which are summarized in Table 1. Both approaches may describe two ways to face form-finding problems of BATH structures. Geometric-driven approaches have made complex numerical form-finding procedures more accessible to a wider range of user designers. The main advantage of independent form-finding stages is that initial geometric models, required for starting the simulation, can be easily parametrized and evaluated through fast convergences of numerical methods. This condition also implies processes focused on mesh types, but not subordinated to specific meshing algorithms. Therefore, geometric-driven approaches are best suited when topologies are more regular and fixed, and can be easily defined through designers' intuitions.

	FORM-FINDING APPROACHES	
	Geometric-driven	Topology-driven
Workflow	Discontinuous	Continuous
Modelling stages	Linear and independent	Circular and recursive
Metric properties	Flexible	Flexible
Non-metric properties	Rigid	Flexible
Design space	Limited	Extended
Interactivity	Limited	Extended
Computational cost	Low	High

Table 1: Major characteristics of both form-finding approaches.

Instead, topology-driven approaches are more suitable when designing complex assemblies of bending- and tensile form-active components. They are primarily focused on exploring the complexity of form and material articulation of component-based structures. Here, the main advantage of interrelated form-finding stages is that simulation can start without an initial geometric model since this one is progressively built during the entire process. In this context, processes are directed by mesh types and specific meshing algorithms. What is most important is that these approaches open the door for new explorations regarding autonomous decision-making strategies through agency, neural networks and evolutionary algorithms. Although topology-driven form-finding approaches are certainly more difficult to implement, they provide users with more flexibility and design space freedom. These conditions may even raise questions about immersive processes for form-finding through virtual and augmented realities.

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